

**PERFORMING ART AS THE METHOD AND TECHNIQUE IN TEACHING
AT PRIMARY SCHOOL LEVEL OF JORHAT DISTRICT, ASSAM (INDIA)
- A CASE STUDY**

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1.0.0. INTRODUCTION

Primary education constitutes a very vital part in the entire structure of educational program. It is at this that the child starts going to a formal education. It means that the child comes directly from home to primary school and has many adjustments. Primary education is that education which is given between 6-14 years age. Primary education is often considered to be the first stage of the entire super structure of educational set up in India. It is primary education which helps in removing mass illiteracy, thus making the most significant contribution to the efficient functioning of democratic institutions. On 26th January, 1950 when India was declared a Republic, the Article 45 of Directive Principles of State Policy was finally accepted. The state shall make an endeavor to provide within a period of ten years from the commencement of the constitution, for free and compulsory education for all children until they complete the age 14 years. But it was not possible for a long time. It is good that the Government of India has passed the Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act-2009, which is popularly known as 'RTE Act-2009'. The District Information System of Education (DISE), 2011-12 reported that in Assam, there are a total of 61,110 schools in the state. In Jorhat district there are 6 Revenue Circles and 8 CD Blocks which comprises 848 villages, 3 numbers of Sub divisions, 111 Gaon panchayat, 1556 numbers of lower primary schools, 318 middle schools, 227 High school (Report of Assam, 2013). A numbers of teaching techniques and tools are used by the teacher to perform their art of teaching for the creating of motivation among the students. Recitation, Storytelling, Drama, mono

acting, games, dancing, using teaching aids, activity methods, lecture methods, project method, inductive-deductive method, heuristic method, demonstration etc. are the useful methods of teaching in Primary school level in our country.

The term teaching method refers to the general principles, pedagogies and management strategies used for classroom instruction. One of the basic truths in education is that the quality of education depends largely upon the quality and teaching techniques and performing art in teaching of teachers. Teaching techniques and teaching strategies are the key to the teaching-learning process. In education, teaching is the concerted sharing of knowledge and experience, which is usually organized within a discipline and, more generally, the provision of stimulus to the psychological and intellectual growth of a person by another person or artifact Teaching method comprises the principles and methods used by teachers to enable student learning. These strategies are determined partly on subject matter to be taught and partly by the nature of the learner. For a particular teaching method to be appropriate and efficient it has to be in relation with the characteristic of the learner and the type of learning it is supposed to bring about. Suggestions are there to design and selection of teaching methods must take into account not only the nature of the subject matter but also how students learn. In today's school the trend is that it encourages a lot of creativity. It is a known fact that human advancement comes through reasoning. This reasoning and original thought enhances creativity.

The approaches for teaching can be broadly classified into teacher centered and student centered. In Teacher-Centered Approach to Learning, Teachers are the main authority figure in this model. Students are viewed as “empty vessels” whose primary role is to passively receive information (via lectures and direct instruction) with an end goal of testing and assessment. It is the primary role of teachers to pass knowledge and information onto their students. In this model, teaching and assessment are viewed as two separate entities. Student learning is measured through objectively scored tests and assessments. In Student-Centered Approach to Learning, while teachers are an authority figure in this model, teachers and students play an

equally active role in the learning process. The teacher's primary role is to coach and facilitate student learning and overall comprehension of material.

2.0.0. OBJECTIVES

- To study the methods of teaching in primary school level in Jorhat district of Assam.
- To study techniques of teaching in primary school level in Jorhat district of Assam.

3.0.0. SIGNIFICANT OF THE STUDY

After independence of our country India; researcher had began to study in the field of Primary education. Since the beginning of research study in Indian Education there are not as many as study had been conducted in the field of primary education. Primary education is considered as the foundation stage and entry of formal education structure of our educational set up. It is primary education which helps in removing illiteracy and development of the literacy in our country. Thus making the most significant contribution to the efficient functioning of democratic country primary education has significant role. Therefore present study has significant role in our education system.

4.0.0. METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey method is used to study the "Performing Art as the Method and Technique in Teaching at Primary School level of Jorhat District"-A case study

4.0.1. Sample

The present study has been conducted on the sample of 10 numbers of primary schools, 10 numbers teachers and 20 numbers of pupils of the Primary schools in Jorhat district of Assam,.

4.0.2. Research Tools for data collection

The researcher has used the following research tools for data collection –

4.0.2.i. Questionnaire

Researcher had constructed and standardized a questionnaire to know the methods and techniques of teaching in primary education. In this regard researcher has developed 10 questions for both pupils and teachers.

4.0.3. Sources of Data

The data for the study have been collected from both primary and secondary Sources. The Primary data have been collected with the help of Questionnaire. The secondary data both published and unpublished are also gathered from the government and departmental records, schools records, District Gazettes, Census report, hand book, News papers, Journal.

5.0.0. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The methods and techniques of primary education are analysed and discussed separately as follows.

Methods of teaching

Teaching method comprises the principles and methods used by teachers to enable student learning. Methods of teaching in primary school level are as follows-

- **Lecturing Method**

The lecture method is convenient for the institution and cost-efficient, especially with larger classroom sizes. Lecture methods help in the classroom at once to address the most people at once, in the most general manner, while still conveying the information that he or she feels is most important, according to the lesson plan. While the lecture method gives the instructor or teacher chances to expose students to unpublished or not readily available material, the students plays a passive role which may hinder learning.

- **Demonstrating Method**

Demonstrating is the process of teaching through examples or experiments. Memorization of a list of facts is a detached and impersonal experience, whereas the same information, conveyed through demonstration, becomes personally relatable. Demonstrations help to raise student interest and reinforce memory retention because they provide connections between facts and real-world applications of those facts.

- **Classroom Discussion Method**

The most common type of collaborative method of teaching in a class is classroom discussion. It is also a democratic way of handling a class, where each student is given equal opportunity to interact and put forth their views. A discussion could also

follow a presentation or a demonstration. Class discussions can enhance student understanding, add context to academic content, broaden student perspectives, highlight opposing viewpoints, reinforce knowledge, build confidence, and support community in learning.

- **Deductive and inductive Method**

Deduction – is the process of solving a problem by applying to the problem or difficulty a generalization already formed. It is the process of thought starting from general going to particular. It can be used for ordinary subject matters and principles in textbooks. It helps students discover important rules or truths for themselves careful observation of enough specific examples that will support the generalization. Inductive methods makes the students think logically and scientifically which is retained longer and is better understood.

- **Heuristic Method**

Heuristic method is a pure discovery method of learning science independent of teacher. In this method the teacher set a problem for the students and then stands aside while discover the answer. The method requires the students to solve a number of problems experimentally. Each student is required to discover everything for himself and is to be told nothing .The students are led to discover facts with the help of experiments, apparatus and books. In this method the children behaves like a research scholar. In the stage managed heuristic method, a problem sheet with minimum instruction is given to the student and he is required to perform the experiments concerning the problem in hand.

- **Problem solving method**

One of the most important aspects of the problem- solving approach to children’s development in scientific thinking is the teachers’ attitude. His approach should be teaching science with a question mark instead of with an exclamation point. The acceptance of and the quest for unique solutions for the problem that the class is investigating should be a guiding principles in the teacher’s approaches to his programme of science. Teachers should be ready to accept any suggestion for the

solution of problem regardless of how irrelevant it may seem to him, for this is really the true spirit of scientific problem solving.

- **Project method**

The project method is a medium of instruction which was introduced during the 18th century. It is child-centered and based in progressive education. Students in a project method environment should be allowed to explore and experience their environment through their senses and, in a sense, direct their own learning by their individual interests. A project method classroom focuses on democracy and collaboration to solve "purposeful" problems. The methods of teaching in Primary school are tabulated as follows.

Table No. 1. Methods of Teaching in Primary school in Jorhat district

Sl. No.	Methods of teaching	Percentage
1.	Lecture Method	90%
2.	Demonstration	80%
3.	Classroom Discussion	65%
4.	Inductive and deductive	50%
5.	Heuristic Method	50%
6.	Problem solving method	60%
7.	Project method	60%

From the table it is found maximum numbers of primary school have used lecture method in their teaching and 50% primary school have used inductive-deductive and Heuristic method in teaching in Jorhat District of Assam.

Figure No.1. Graphical representation of Percentage of methods of teaching

Above graphical representation is the evidence of Methods of teaching in primary school in Jorhat district.

Techniques of teaching

Traditional teaching techniques, based mainly on a teacher explaining a topic and students taking notes, may still be useful on occasion, but education today revolves more around encouraging the student to awaken their curiosity and desire to learn. A number of different teaching techniques have emerged due to this change in education. Many of these teaching techniques are not actually new however! The use of technology in the classroom has simply given education a new lease of life allowing us to approach old ideas in new ways. Outlined below are some popular teaching techniques that have arisen from the integration of technology in education.

- **Recitation**

Recitation is innovative techniques of teaching. The modern concept of the recitations mentions its place for developing reflective thinking, creative expression, favorable attitudes, and ideals of social living, developing many skills, attitudes, abilities, and ideals. Freedom of expression and respect for the opinions of others are encouraged. The recitation in the modern classroom serves many purposes. The teacher should have a high standard of performance for all activities. Students should recite for the class, not for the teacher alone.

- **Story Telling**

In its simplest form, storytelling remains a powerful element of communication, with the narrative being equally as compelling as essays and textbooks. Stories touch our emotions and make us laugh, cry, fear, and get angry etc. Story telling is another innovation technique in teaching. A true story our own life, a true story from the life of someone, a true story from the news or a current event, a story that took place sometime in history, a fictional story, with made up characters or events etc are different types of story. Of course, there are various genres and styles of storytelling, but the above list represents the essential variety that we might incorporate into the classroom. But it is essential that children understand how to tell a good story and how this relates to effectively accomplishing an objective.

- **Drama**

Drama is an Effective technique of teaching in Elementary school which can help the pupils to understand the subject matter easily. “Drama is powerful because its unique balance of thought and feeling makes learning exciting, challenging relevant to real-life concerns, and enjoyable” Research indicates that using drama in the classroom as a means of teaching helps students learn academically, socially, and developmentally. “The use of drama as a tool for teaching is not new. Historically, both drama and theatre have long been recognized as potent means of education and indoctrination. Teaching using drama brings emotion and learning together. Most importantly of all, using drama to teach in the elementary classroom gets students involved and gives them the power to have a key role in their education.

- **Gaming**

Learning through the use of games is one of the teaching methods that have already been explored especially in elementary and preschool education. By using games, students learn without even realizing. Therefore, learning through play or ‘*Gamification*‘ is a learning technique that can be very effective at any age. It is also a very useful technique to keep students motivated.

Games make learning concepts more palatable for students and supply learners with a platform for their creative thoughts to bounce around.

Games encourage creative behavior and divergent thought (Fuszard, 2001) and are excellent ice breakers.

- **Dancing**

Dancing is another type of teaching techniques in primary school level which help the pupil to understand the subject matter easily.

- **Teaching Aids**

As we all know that today's age is the age of science and technology. The teaching learning programs have also been affected by it. The process of teaching - learning depends upon the different type of equipment available in the classroom. There are three types of teaching aids they are- Visual aids like- actual objects, models,

pictures, charts, maps, flash cards, flannel board, bulletin board, chalkboard, overhead projector, slides etc. Audio Aids which involve the sense of hearing are called Audio aids like- radio, tape recorder, gramophone etc. and Audio - Visual Aids which involve the sense of vision as well as hearing like- television, film projector, film strips etc. teaching can create motivation easily among the pupils.

Table No. 2. Techniques of teaching in Primary school level

Sl no.	Techniques of teaching	Percentage
1.	Recitation	75%
2.	Story telling	60%
3.	Drama	60%
4.	Gaming	70%
5.	Dancing	70%
6.	Teaching aids	95%

Above table is the evidence of different teaching techniques which are used by the teachers of primary school level in Jorhat district of Assam.

Figure No. 2. Graphical representation of Techniques of teaching in Primary school level

Above Graphical representation shows the percentages of techniques of teaching in Primary school level of Jorhat district in Assam.

6.0.0. Findings

From the analysis of the data following finding are found.

- Form the investigation it is found that 90% of Primary School teachers use Lecture method in their teaching in Jorhat District of Assam.
- The study shows that 80% Primary school teachers in Jorhat District use Demonstration method in teaching.
- 65% of Primary school Teachers use Class room Discussion in their teaching of Jorhat district in Assam.
- The study shows that only 50% Primary schools in Jorhat District use inductive and deductive method and Heuristic method in teaching.
- Form the investigation it is found that 60% of Primary School teachers use problem solving and project method in their teaching in Primary school level in Jorhat of Assam.
- Form the investigation it is found that 75% of Primary School teachers use Recitation techniques of teaching in their teaching in Jorhat District of Assam.
- The study shows that 60% Primary school teachers in Jorhat District use the techniques of storytelling techniques in teaching.
- 60% of Primary school Teachers shows Drama in the Class room for creating motivation in their teaching of Jorhat district in Assam.
- The study shows that only 70% Primary schools teacher in Jorhat District use Gaming techniques in their teaching.
- Form the study it is found that 70% of Primary School teachers use dancing techniques in their teaching in Primary school level in Jorhat of Assam.
- From the study it is investigated that maximum numbers (95%) of primary school teachers use teaching aids in their teaching in Jorhat district of Assam.

7.0.0. Conclusion

Primary education is the foundation stage of education system in our country. It is the first formal and compulsory education process in our education system. In the primary school - lecture method, discussion method, project method, heuristics methods etc are using in teaching process of the teachers. The teachers in primary level use different techniques in their teaching to creating motivation and interest

among the pupil. Besides the traditional methods and techniques of teaching in the primary school the teachers are using different modern methods and techniques in their teaching of the country. The Primary schools in urban area and private school are more advance than the using of teaching methods and techniques in rural and Government school in Assam.

6.0.0. References:

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